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Prolyl hydroxylase induction during TNBC resistance.

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We provide evidence here for activation of prolyl hydroxylases in resistance to chemotherapy in TNBC cells. *P3H3* was activated. The change may have been associated with a hypoxic type response, which featured activation of *Egln-3* and *Egln-1*.

Citations

1. Hudson, D.M., Weis, M., Rai, J., Joeng, K.S., Dimori, M., Lee, B.H., Morello, R. and Eyre, D.R., 2017. P3h3-null and Sc65-null mice phenocopy the collagen lysine under-hydroxylation and cross-linking abnormality of Ehlers-Danlos syndrome type VIA. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 292(9), pp.3877-3887.